

NBI Small Research Grants Program 2012 – Project Report

Project Title: Moth Mania – A Citizen Scientist Survey of the Moths of Nantucket

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Abstract

The goal of this project was to record and raise public awareness about the diversity of moth fauna on Nantucket through a three-day summer “Moth Blitz.” Public events were held where stations set up to attract moths were staffed by photographers with “mothing” experience and the public was encouraged to explore the various creatures that showed up and to learn more about the world of nighttime insect fauna. Photographers documented all moth species observed at the stations and found 125 different species across 19 different families, including 24 that do not appear to have been recorded on island in the past. Through this project, we contributed numerous Nantucket and Massachusetts records to online databases and greatly expanded the online public records of Nantucket moth fauna.

Introduction

Moths are a greatly unappreciated group of insects. Smaller and often less brightly colored than their Lepidopteran cousins, the butterflies, their nocturnal habits mean they are not often seen. They may even uniformly be dismissed as pest organisms because of a few well-known species. But in fact moths are an incredibly diverse, beautiful part of Class Insecta.

Over the past decade, the advent of cheap digital macro photography has led to growth in the number of amateur and professional “mothing” hobbyists and photographers. These enthusiasts track moths in their neighborhoods and beyond, attracting specimens using lighting, sheets and sometimes food bait. This data is frequently shared online, and the advent of online insect databases and photo collections had led to a greater understanding of moth diversity throughout North America. Yet with all this online collaboration, the information out there for Nantucket Island remains sparse. February 2012 records from two of the most popular online insect photo repositories, BugGuide (<http://bugguide.net>) and the Butterflies and Moths of North America (BAMONA) website (<http://www.butterfliesandmoths.org>) indicated merely 8 and 34 Nantucket records, respectively, out of hundreds from Massachusetts.

This project was designed as an opportunity to not only expand the understanding of moth diversity on Nantucket, but also to create an online resource for Nantucket moth fauna, something that would benefit researchers and educators both on island and off. With that in mind, we developed three project goals:

- 1) Observe, record and report moth diversity at overnight Nantucket “Moth Blitzes.”
- 2) Establish a semi-permanent “mothing” station at the UMass Boston Nantucket Field Station.
- 3) Cultivate a better understanding of moths, and encourage Citizen Scientist monitoring and reporting of moth species on Nantucket.

Methods

- 1) **Moth Blitzes:** We recruited participants experienced in “mothing” as well as other biologists both on and off island to join us for surveys in early August. We worked with the Nantucket Field Station to determine feasible locations and a time frame and settled on the following:
 - Friday, August 4, Nantucket Field Station
 - Saturday, August 5, evening at Gouin Village
 - Sunday, August 6, day trip to Sconset Dump, and evening at Linda Loring Nature Foundation

The three evening sites selected differed in their habitat and land use types, with the Nantucket Field Station having freshwater and field habitats, Gouin Village being highly managed and in a heavily settled area, and the Linda Loring Foundation headquarters adjacent to a large pine forest. Each event was set up with both light displays (mercury vapor or CFL bulbs against white sheets for reflectivity) and bait stations (fermented juices painted on tree trunks) to attract the moths.

The team we brought to the island included Seabrooke Leckie, co-author of the recent Peterson Guide to Moths of the Northeast. The Friday night and Sunday night events were prefaced by book-signings and also by a lecture about the world of moths given by

David Small. The Nantucket Field Station assisted us by publicizing the events on-island. At each event, our four key photographers (Lula Field, Bo Zaremba, Jennifer Forman Orth and Dave Small) attempted to capture images of every single moth species observed. Over the next several months, each photographer then identified all his/her photos to the lowest taxonomic level possible. All records are being kept in a Google Spreadsheet shared among the photographers in order to facilitate identifications (and changes, if necessary) and to keep track of the number of species found.

In order to compare our finds with preexisting data, we procured a digital copy of “The Lepidoptera of Nantucket and Martha’s Vineyard Islands, Massachusetts,” (Jones & Kimball, 1943). Following manipulation of this dataset to account for recent changes in moth taxonomy, the 1943 data was compared to species found during our 2013 mothing events. In addition, we also incorporated the data on macromoths (families of larger moth species) available through Mark Mello’s online species database (<http://lloydcenter.org/nantucket-lepidoptera/>) and compared our finds to this list as well.

2) **Mothing Stations:** Prior to our arrival on the island, we developed an equipment list and began purchasing the materials we would need for the mothing events:

- Sheets and clips to secure them
- Mercury vapor lamps and CFL bulbs (light with wavelengths known to attract moths), along with stands, shields, etc. to secure the lamps
- Extension cords (for setups near power supplies) and external power supplies (so that participants can set up sheets anywhere)
- Several pairs of UV goggles in order to promote vision safety for any future participants

This equipment, which included some items purchased directly by the Nantucket Field Station, was left at the Field Station lab after the events, so that they can set up future mothing events and/or loan out equipment at their discretion to interested parties.

3) **Cultivate Appreciation of Moths:** The experts we brought to the island made it a point to engage with the attendees at the events, explaining our simple setup and encouraging

interaction with the insects that showed up at the lights. Following the event, the key photographers of specimens reached out online to show off interesting finds and to determine the id of various specimens. All identified photos were placed online on Discover Life to act as digital vouchers (http://pick14.pick.uga.edu/mp/20p?res=320&see=I_ORT/0000&flags=order_by_title).

Results

- 1) **Moth Blitzes:** During the three day trip to Nantucket we recorded approximately 125 different moth species (see Appendix 1). Of those, we could identify 123 to family, and recorded species in 19 different families (see Appendix 2), with the most commonly represented families being the Noctuidae (25), the Erebidae (19), the Geometridae (15) and the Crambidae (14). With data from four different photographers who were each at the same events, we found that a species was most likely to be noticed and photographed by a single person (38% of the time) or by everyone (24% of the time), meaning that even with significant crowds at the lights, it was still possible for a single person with a camera to capture a species that no one else saw.

An analysis of Jones & Kimball's "The Lepidoptera of Nantucket and Martha's Vineyard Islands, Massachusetts" indicates approximately 924 moth species on Nantucket, represented by 46 different families. Mark Mello's database of Nantucket macromoths (<http://lloydcenter.org/nantucket-lepidoptera/>) lists approximately 732 species in 11 different families.

Our data, collected over three days in August 2012, represented roughly 10% of the moth fauna of Nantucket. Of our own photographed moths, 94 were matched to records in either Jones & Kimball, Mello, or both (this includes 8 species recorded by Jones & Kimball on Martha's Vineyard but not Nantucket). This includes 61 species recorded in both published sources (including four recorded by Jones & Kimball as present on Martha's Vineyard but not on Nantucket). Twenty-three of the species recorded during the 2012 Nantucket Moth Blitz were not listed in either of the published records of Nantucket moth data, and those are included in this report in Appendix 3.

Eighteen of the moths we photographed were not identifiable to species, either because the photos did not capture enough identifiable characters, because the specimen was too worn, or because specimens could not be identified to species without genital dissection or DNA barcoding. Of these 18, we believe that two, which were identifiable to genus, *Ancylis* sp. (Tortricidae) and *Coleotechnites* sp. (Gelechiidae), are distinct enough that we can say they are not listed in either Jones & Kimball or Mello.

- 2) **Nothing Stations:** All equipment purchased was checked and deployed during the Moth Blitz events (Aug. 4-6 2012) and Nantucket Field Station staff were advised on how and where to set up nothing stations. Equipment is being stored on site at the Nantucket Field Station lab.
- 3) **Cultivate Appreciation of Moths:** The evening events held August 4 and 6 were fairly well attended, with approximately 15 Nantucket residents, students, and visiting scientists present at the Nantucket Field Station event, and approximately 20 participants at the Linda Loring Nature Foundation event, including several families with children (see photos in Appendix 4). Several participants purchased copies of the Peterson Moth Guide.

Following the field events, our key photographers posted their finds online, and added several new state records to the online databases at BugGuide (<http://bugguide.net>) and the Butterflies and Moths of North America (BAMONA) website (<http://www.butterfliesandmoths.org>).

Discussion

We willingly acknowledge that identification of moths to species using photographs can be tricky and may not always be possible. For several specimens that we photographed, we are either still waiting on species confirmation or have determined that it is not possible to get past genus. Identification is further complicated by taxonomic changes that make comparison of records even a decade old challenging. However, out of the 125 distinct species we photographed

during the Moth Blitz, we were still able to id 107 to species level, a success rate of 86%, and we expect this rate to increase following consultation with experts regarding some of our unknown micromoths (families of smaller moths). We also found more than 20 species for which there appears to be no previous published record of their presence on Nantucket. Given the time and expertise required to capture, preserve and examine specimens in order to guarantee the maximum number are identified to species level, we consider photography to be a viable option for anyone to make a significant contribution to the knowledge of moth fauna in an area, provided the photographer is cautious about not pronouncing a photo to be of a certain species in cases where it is more appropriate to stop at the genus level.

Our documentation of species not previously noted on the island is not surprising given that Mello (<http://lloydcenter.org/nantucket-lepidoptera>) found that, looking at 11 families of macromoths, that there was a 38% difference between what he found from 2000-2006 and what Kimball had found in 1943. Unfortunately, we cannot compare our findings directly to Mello's because his online database includes only macromoths, but we did find three Noctuid species (*Acronicta hamamelis*, *Calloplistria floridensis*, and *Hyperstrotia flaviguttata*) that Mello did not appear to have listed. When comparing our list of moths to Jones & Kimball's 1943 compilation, we do potentially contribute an additional 23 species to this list. This is not unexpected, given the continued import of plants to the island for landscaping, gardening, etc. as well as the potential accidental introduction of moths as hitchhikers (as eggs, larvae or adults) on goods and vehicles transported to the island.

Perhaps the most powerful result of this effort to document moth fauna on Nantucket is that we can take this data and place it online, making it freely accessible to anyone with internet access to explore. The online photographic records for moths remain paltry, particularly for the microlepidoptera, and for many interested in studying moths these records are an important tool in the id process. Since our trip in August 2012, BugGuide.net has 21 new moth records from Nantucket, and five of these (*Ancylis mira*, *Argyria rufisignella*, *Choristoneura obsoletana*, *Schizura apicalis*, *Zanclognatha theralis*) are the first Massachusetts records in the guide. BAMONA now has 107 species records for Nantucket, an increase of over 300% from before we began this project (see

http://www.butterfliesandmoths.org/checklists?species_type=1&tid=1407). We will continue to maintain a photographic catalog of our finds through the Discover Life website and hope to update it as we learn more about some of our as yet unidentified photos (http://pick14.pick.uga.edu/mp/20p?res=320&see=I_ORI/0000&flags=order_by_title:).

We believe this effort to document moth fauna on Nantucket was a successful venture that allowed us not only to add new species records to the Nantucket knowledge base, but also to empower anyone the island who is interested to continue this effort to document species for many years to come. Now that the Nantucket Field Station has the tools in hand to continue this work annually, we encourage the island to start by participating in the 2013 National Moth Week, July 20-28. With the ability to photodocument even tiny micromoths using standard camera equipment, we believe Citizen Scientists could potentially add a lot to the knowledge base of moth species on Nantucket.

Acknowledgements

We are extremely grateful to the Nantucket Field Station and Sarah Oktay for supporting this project, and helping us to arrange field sites, travel and lodging for the trip. The P.I.'s were joined on the trip by Bo Zarembo, Lula Field, Gwen Pearson and Seabrooke Leckie, who tirelessly provided their photographic and taxonomic expertise to track down and identify as many species as possible and to interact with other Moth Blitz participants in ways that encouraged a future interest in moths. Charley Eiseman was able to join us briefly for two of the nights as well, and his records are included in our species list. Paul Goldstein provided the electronic version of Jones & Kimball without which much of the above analysis would not have been possible. Mark Mello generously took time out of his busy schedule to provide background information used to prepare the grant proposal. Several taxonomic experts and "amateur mothers" provided identification assistance to us, including: Hugh McGuinness, Ken Childs, Barbara Spencer, and Sue Cloutier...to them we are most grateful because they proceeded in the spirit of this effort to rely on "digital vouchers" to compile taxonomic data.

Literature Cited:

Jones, Frank Morton and Kimball, Charles P. "The Lepidoptera of Nantucket and Marthas Vineyard Islands, Massachusetts" 1943. Maria Mitchell Association.

Mello, Mark. Nantucket Lepidoptera (database). 2006. Last accessed February 2013.
<http://lloydcenter.org/nantucket-lepidoptera/>

Tables and Figures

Appendix 1: Species list (please note some ids are questionable and may be subject to change, the original document is held at

<https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/cc?key=0At8VJwwb9186dDRsTXhHckktSIVMV0tGcIFTOVNGLUE&usp=sharing>)

Family	Genus	Species	Common Name	Hodges #
Acrolophidae	Acrolophus	sp.	tubeworm moth	
Coleophoridae	Blastobasis	glandulella	Acorn Moth	1162
Coleophoridae	Coleophora	sp.		
Coleophoridae	Pigritia	sp.		
Crambidae	Argyria	rufisignella	Mother-of-pearl Moth	5462
Crambidae	Desmia	funeralis	Grape Leafroller	5159
Crambidae	Donacaula	roscidellus	Brown Donacaula	5321
Crambidae	Eustixia	pupula	Spotted Peppergrass Moth	4794
Crambidae	Fissicrambus	mutabilis	changeable grass veneer	5435
Crambidae	Herpetogramma	abdominalis		5276
Crambidae	Herpetogramma	thestealis	Zigzag Herpetogramma	5277
Crambidae	Microcrambus	elegans	Elegant Grass-veneer Moth	5420
Crambidae	Neodactria	luteolellus	mottled grass veneer	5379
Crambidae	Nomophila	nearctica	Lucerne Moth	5156
Crambidae	Parapoynx	seminealis	Floating-heart Waterlily Moth	4763
Crambidae	Synclita	obliteralis	Waterlily Leafcutter Moth	4755
Crambidae	Urola	nivalis	Snowy Urola	5464
Crambidae			unknown brown crambid	
Elachistidae	Agonopterix	pulvipennella		867
Elachistidae	Chrysoclista	linneella	Linden Bark-borer	1463
Erebidae	Apantesis	phalerata	Harnessed Moth	8169
Erebidae	Bleptina	caradrinalis	bent-winged owlet	8370
Erebidae	Catocala	praeclara	Praeclara Underwing	8865
Erebidae	Catocala	ultronia	Ultronia Underwing	8857
Erebidae	Crambidia	pallida	Pale Lichen Moth	8045.1
Erebidae	Dasychira	sp.	variable tussock moth	8294
Erebidae	Halysidota	sp.	Banded Tussock Moth	8203
Erebidae	Hypena	manalis	Flowing-line snout	8441
Erebidae	Hypena	palparia	Mottled snout	8444
Erebidae	Hypena	scabra	Green Cloverworm	8465
Erebidae	Lophocampa	caryae	Hickory Tussock Moth	8211
Erebidae	Macrochilo	orciferalis	bronzy Macrochilo	8360
Erebidae	Orgyia	leucostigma	White-marked Tussock Moth	8316
Erebidae	Pangrapta	decoralis	Decorated Owlet	8490

Erebidae	Panopoda	rufimargo	Red-lined Panopoda	8587
Erebidae	Renia	discoloralis	Discolored Renia	8381
Erebidae	Renia	flavipunctalis	Yellow-spotted Renia	8384.1
Erebidae	Zale	lunata	Lunate Zale	8689
Erebidae	Zanclognatha	theralis		8341
Gelechiidae	Aroga	epigaeela		2189
Gelechiidae	Chionodes	formosella	Spring Oak Leafroller	2077
Gelechiidae	Coleotechnites	sp.		
Gelechiidae	Dichomeris	serrativittella complex		2301
Geometridae	Costaconvexa	centrostrigaria	Bent-line Carpet	7416
Geometridae	Cyclophora	pendulinaria	Sweetfern Geometer	7139
Geometridae	Ectropis	crepuscularia	Small Engrailed	6597
Geometridae	Eulithis	diversilineata	Lesser Grapevine Looper	7196
Geometridae	Eupithecia	miserulata	common pug	7474
Geometridae	Glena	cognataria	blueberry gray	6450
Geometridae	Lobocleta	ossularia	Drab Brown Wave	7094
Geometridae	Metanema	inatomaria	Pale Metanema	6819
Geometridae	Nematocampa	resistaria	Horned Spanworm	7010
Geometridae	Pero	morrisonaria	Morrison's Pero	6755
Geometridae	Plagodis	pulveraria	American Barred Umber	6836
Geometridae	Pleuroprucha	insulsaria	Common Tan Wave	7132
Geometridae	Prochoerodes	lineola	Large Maple Spanworm	6982
Geometridae	Scopula	inductata	Simple Wave	7164
Geometridae			unknown geometrid "macro"	
Gracillariinae	Caloptilia	rhoifoliella	Sumac Leafblotch Miner	630
Limacodidae	Lithacodes	fasciola	Yellow-shouldered Slug Moth	4665
Noctuidae	Abagrotis	alternata	Greater Red Dart	11029
Noctuidae	Acronicta	hamamelis	Witch Hazel Dagger Moth	9248
Noctuidae	Acronicta	oblinita	Smeared Dagger Moth	9272
Noctuidae	Agriopodes	fallax	Green Marvel	9281
Noctuidae	Agrotis	ipsilon	Ipsilon Dart	10663
Noctuidae	Amphipyra	pyramidoides	Copper Underwing	9638
Noctuidae	Callopietria	cordata	Silver-spotted Fern Moth	9633
Noctuidae	Callopietria	floridensis	Florida Fern Moth	9630
Noctuidae	Callopietria	mollissima	Pink-shaded Fern Moth	9631
Noctuidae	Dargida	diffusa	Wheat Head Armyworm	10431
Noctuidae	Deltote	bellicula	Bog Deltote	9046
Noctuidae	Derrima	stellata	Pink Star Moth	11055
Noctuidae	Eudryas	grata	beautiful wood nymph	9301
Noctuidae	Euplexia	benesimilis	American Angle Shades	9545
Noctuidae	Gabara	subnivosella	wet sand savannah moth	8522
Noctuidae	Galgula	partita	Wedgling	9688

Noctuidae	Harrisimemna	tresignata	Harris' Three-spot	9286
Noctuidae	Hyperstrotia	flaviguttata	Yellow-spotted Graylet	9039
Noctuidae	Leucania	phragmitidicola	Phragmites Wainscot	10444
Noctuidae	Mythimna	unipuncta	Armyworm	10438
Noctuidae	Noctua	pronuba	Large Yellow Underwing	11003.1
Noctuidae	Phosphila	miselioides	Spotted Phosphila	9619
Noctuidae	Pseudeustrotia	carneola	Pink-barred Pseudeustrotia	9053
Noctuidae	Schinia	lynx	Lynx Flower Moth	11117
Noctuidae	Spodoptera	ornithogalli	Yellow-striped Armyworm	9669
Nolidae	Meganola	minuscula	Confused Meganola	8983
Nolidae	Nola	clethrae	Sweet Pepperbush Nola Moth	8996
Notodontidae	Oligocentria	semirufescens	Red-washed Prominent	8012
Notodontidae	Schizura	apicalis	Plain Schizura	8009
Notodontidae	Schizura	unicornis	Unicorn Caterpillar Moth	8007
Notodontidae	Symmerista	albifrons	White-headed Prominent	7951
Oecophoridae	Antaeotricha	schlaegeri	Schlaeger's Fruitworm	1011
Oecophoridae	Decantha	boreasella	reticulated Decantha	1042
Plutellidae	Plutella	xylostella	diamondback moth	2366
Pterophoridae	Geina	sp.	plume moth	
Pterophoridae	Hellinsia	sp.	plume moth	
Pyalidae	Dioryctria	disclusa	Webbing Coneworm	5847
Pyalidae	Dolichomia	olinalis	Yellow-fringed Dolichomia	5533
Pyalidae	Elophila	icciusalis	Pondside Pyralid	4748
Pyalidae	Etiella	zinckenella	Gold-banded Etiella Moth	5744
Pyalidae	Peoria	approximella	Carmine Snout	6053
Sphingidae	Darapsa	choerilus	Azalea Sphinx	7886
Sphingidae	Paonias	myops	Small-eyed Sphinx	7825
Sphingidae	Sphinx	kalmiae	Laurel Sphinx	7809
Tortricidae	Ancylis	mira		3368
Tortricidae	Acleris	fragariana	strawberry Acleris	3532
Tortricidae	Ancylis	sp.		
Tortricidae	Argyrotaenia	sp.		
Tortricidae	Argyrotaenia	velutinana	Red-banded Leafroller	3597
Tortricidae	Cenopis	reticulatana	reticulated fruitworm	3720
Tortricidae	Choristoneura	obsoletana		3631
Tortricidae	Cacoecimorpha	pronubana	carnation Tortrix moth	3678
Tortricidae	Cydia	latiferreana	Filbertworm	3494
Tortricidae	Eucosma	cataclystiana	Solidago Eucosma	3142
Tortricidae	Eucosma	derelicta	derelict Eucosma	3120
Tortricidae	Olethreutes	valdanum		2812
Tortricidae	Phaneta	raracana		2928
Tortricidae	Platynota	flavedana	Black-shaded Platynota	3732
Tortricidae	Zomaria	interruptolineana	Broken-line Zomaria	2750

Tortricidae			unknown orangey Tort	
Tortricidae			unknown tiny beige Tort	
Tortricidae			unknown brocaded grey Tort	
Yponomeutidae	Atteva	aurea	Ailanthus Webworm	2401
			unknown tiny patterned gray micro	
			unidentified tiny gold bullet micro	

Appendix 2: Representation by taxonomic family of the moths identified at the Nantucket Moth Blitz, with individuals from 19 different families.

Family	Count
Acrolophidae	1
Coleophoridae	3
Crambidae	14
Elachistidae	2
Erebidae	19
Gelechiidae	4
Geometridae	15
Gracillariinae	1
Limacodidae	1
Noctuidae	25
Nolidae	2
Notodontidae	4
Oecophoridae	2
Plutellidae	1
Pterophoridae	2
Pyralidae	5
Sphingidae	3
Tortricidae	18
Yponomeutidae	1
Grand Total	123

Appendix 3: Species recorded during the 2012 Nantucket Moth Blitz that were not found in Jones & Kimball (1943) or Mello (2006, last accessed 2013):

Family	Genus	Species
Coleophoridae	<i>Blastobasis</i>	<i>glandulella</i>
Crambidae	<i>Argyria</i>	<i>rufisignella</i>
Crambidae	<i>Donacaula</i>	<i>roscidellus</i>
Crambidae	<i>Herpetogramma</i>	<i>abdominalis</i>
Crambidae	<i>Herpetogramma</i>	<i>thestealis</i>
Crambidae	<i>Nomophila</i>	<i>nearctica</i>
Elachistidae	<i>Agonopterix</i>	<i>pulvipennella</i>
Elachistidae	<i>Chrysoclista</i>	<i>linneella</i>
Gelechiidae	<i>Aroga</i>	<i>epigaeella</i>
Gelechiidae	<i>Chionodes</i>	<i>formosella</i>
Gelechiidae	<i>Coleotechnites</i>	sp.
Gelechiidae	<i>Dichomeris</i>	<i>serrativittella</i> complex
Gracillariidae	<i>Caloptilia</i>	<i>rhoifoliella</i>
Noctuidae	<i>Acronicta</i>	<i>hamamelis</i>
Noctuidae	<i>Callopietria</i>	<i>floridensis</i>
Noctuidae	<i>Hyperstrotia</i>	<i>flaviguttata</i>
Oecophoridae	<i>Antaeotricha</i>	<i>schlaegeri</i>
Pyralidae	<i>Dolichomia</i>	<i>olinalis</i>
Tortricidae	<i>Acleris</i>	<i>fragariana</i>
Tortricidae	<i>Ancylis</i>	<i>mira</i>
Tortricidae	<i>Cacoecimorpha</i>	<i>pronubana</i>
Tortricidae	<i>Choristoneura</i>	<i>obsoletana</i>
Tortricidae	<i>Olethreutes</i>	<i>valdanum</i>

Appendix 4: Photos from the 2012 Nantucket Moth Blitz (Photographer: Gwen Pearson)

